

FIRST DESIGN OF A 10 TeV CENTRE OF MASS ENERGY MUON COLLIDER*

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Abstract

The design of a muon collider complex requires to overcome challenges associated with muons short lifetime. To reach the expected luminosity for a multi TeV muon collider ring an interaction region with beta values of the order of a few millimetres is required. Resulting challenges are the development of a chromatic compensation section that is not degrading the physical and dynamical aperture, while allowing the control of the momentum compaction factor, as well as the control of the radiation due to muons reaching the earth surface. A preliminary version of a 10 TeV centre-of-mass energy muon collider ring fulfilling these requirements and taking limitations from the detector and magnet design into account is presented.

INTRODUCTION

For the post High Luminosity Large Hadron Collider (HL-LHC) [1] era, different new collider projects like the IMCC [2], FCC [3] and CLIC [4] are proposed and studied to explore their physics discovery potential.

A muon collider, due to strong suppression of synchrotron radiation (muons are about 200 times heavier than electrons), can provide high energy (multi-TeV) collisions using fundamental (point-like) particles improving that way the energy frontiers of lepton machines. The idea of using muons is not new and it was initially discussed in [5, 6] and studied by several collaborations [7–9, 11]. Recently, a new International Muon Collider Collaboration (IMCC) was formed and a part of its tasks is to study the possibility to develop a 10 TeV center of mass energy muon collider that is expected to require less power than CLIC at 3 TeV. An additional unique feature of muon colliders is the significant improvement of the luminosity per beam power with beam energy. The compactness of the muon collider complex is expected to allow a cost effective facility provided numerous technical challenges can be overcome.

In the present study, the current status of the 10 TeV collider ring that is based on earlier studies [7, 10, 11] is shown.

COLLIDER RING DESIGN

An illustration of the planned muon accelerator complex can be seen in Fig. 1, while, in Table 1, the main parameters of the collider ring can be found. In order to retain high precision for physics discovery, the 10 TeV center of mass energy ($\sqrt{s} = 10$ TeV) muon collider ring aims to produce integrated luminosity equal to 10 ab^{-1} per IP. To maximize

Figure 1: A conceptual scheme of the muon collider complex.

the luminosity with the limited available muon intensity, only two high intensity bunches ($N_p = 1.8 \times 10^{12}$) of μ^+ and μ^- will be injected at a time and two interaction points (IPs) with very small β^* values ($\beta_x^* = \beta_y^* = 1.5 \text{ mm}$) will be used. The small β^* values in combination with the large momentum spread ($\sigma_{p_T} = 0.1\%$) lead to stringent requirements. Chromatic effects cannot be compensated globally, but require the development of a challenging chromatic compensation section. In order to limit the loss in luminosity due to the hourglass effect, the bunch length has to remain short in the order of β^* over more than 1000 turns. Thus, linear and non-linear momentum compaction have to be controlled very precisely. For the RF requirements, a modest system without particular constraints on the frequency is needed for the compensation of the synchrotron radiation losses but not for longitudinal stability due to excessive RF voltages and very high frequencies needed.

Due to the short muon lifetime ($\tau_0 \approx 2.2 \text{ s}$), the muons path from the production up to collisions must be as short as possible and that raises different design challenges (need for high magnetic fields, fast cooling and acceleration, etc.). For the collider ring, important issues are caused by muon decays ($\mu^+ \rightarrow \bar{\nu}_\mu + \nu_e + e^+$ and $\mu^- \rightarrow \nu_\mu + \bar{\nu}_e + e^-$). Electrons and positrons and showers created by them have to be intercepted by an absorber inside the magnet aperture increasing the aperture and complicating the magnets design. Neutrinos are generated with a small divergence around the direction of the decaying muon and most of them reach the earth surface and generate radiation, which must remain negligible. To this end, straight sections except the ones housing the experiments have to be limited. Thus, combined function magnets (dipole plus a higher order multipole) are used for focusing and non-linear correction, with straight sections between magnets of only 30 cm. As a result of the extensive use of dipolar fields, the collider ring has a racetrack shape, where the two IRs and any insertion devices

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are located at the two straight sections. Another issue due to the decay products and more so due to secondary and tertiary interactions at the IR is the generation of an intense beam-induced background (BIB) around the detectors area. In order to mitigate this and improve the accuracy of physics measurements, special designs of the interaction region are under study [12, 13].

Table 1: 10 TeV Center of Mass Energy Muon Collider

Parameters	Symbol	$\sqrt{s} = 10$ TeV
Particle energy [GeV]	E	5000
Luminosity [$10^{34} \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$]	\mathcal{L}	20
Bunch population [10^{12}]	N_p	1.8
Transverse normalized rms emittance [μm]	ε_n	25
Transverse geometric rms emittance [nm]	ε_g	0.528
Longitudinal emittance ($4\pi \sigma_E \sigma_T$) [eVs]	ε_l	0.314
Longitudinal geometric emittance ($\frac{\varepsilon_l c}{4\pi E_0 \mu}$) [mm]	ε_{lg}	70
Rms bunch length [mm]	σ_z	1.5
Relative rms energy spread [%]	σ_{pT}	0.1
Beta function at IP [mm]	β^*	1.5
Power per beam with 5 Hz repetition rate [MW]	P_{beam}	7.2

Extended Final Focusing Section

The extended final focusing (EFF) of the current version of the muon collider ring shown in Fig. 2a includes the final focusing quadrupoles (FFQ), the chromatic correction sections (CC) and the matching section (MA) that matches the optics to the ones at the arc entrance. In this plot, as well as in the following similar plots, the location and the length of the dipoles, quadrupoles, dipole-quadrupole and dipole-sextupole magnets are shown with light red, light blue, hashed blue and light red with yellow boxes, respectively. The orientation of these elements indicates the polarity (pointing upward/downward for positive/negative k_n). With red, blue and green curves are also plotted the optical β_x , β_y and dispersion (D_x) functions, respectively.

The straight section right after the IP ($s = 0$) include the $L^* = 6$ m and the FFQ for which the maximum magnetic field at the magnet aperture is set to 20 T (assuming the use of HTS). Given the large divergence around the IP, three short quadrupoles with non equal k_1 are used in this area in order to fully benefit from the maximum allowed magnetic field reducing that way the length of the FFQ section. The following four quads are used to control the beta values ($\beta_{x,y}$) and their derivatives ($\alpha_{x,y}$) at the end of the FFQ section. With this version of the collider, at the end of the FFQ, the $\beta_{x,y}$ are two order of magnitudes smaller than their maximum values while $\alpha_{x,y} = 0$ (point to parallel matching).

Figure 2: Evolution of a) the optical functions and b) the phase advance and Montague chromatic functions in the right side of the extended final focusing scheme.

Due to the strong quadrupoles in the FFQ scheme (needed for very small β^*) and the large energy spread ($\sigma_{pT} = 0.1\%$), the linear and non-linear chromatic phenomena are also strong. More specifically, the Montague chromatic functions ($W_{x,y}$) [14] that describe the optics mismatch of off-momentum particles w.r.t on-momentum ones are quite large, as shown in Fig. 2b. For the compensation of such large W functions at the end of the EFF section, a local CC scheme is developed right after the FFQs. The maximum magnetic field for that lattice section (CC), as well as in the following matching section (MA) is assumed to be 16 T. The CC scheme includes two sets of dipole-sextupole magnets, the first one primarily acting on W_y while the other one on W_x . These dipole-sextupole magnets are 1 m long and are placed at positions where the β_y and β_x are maximum, respectively. In order to compensate the resonance driving terms excited by the sextupolar components, the dipole-sextupole magnets of a given set are separated by a -I transformation. Additionally, the phase advance μ_y (μ_x) between the IP and the first (third) dipole-sextupole magnet are kept close to 0.75 (2.25) [2π] for a better control of the higher order chromatic effects.

In the MA section that follows the last dipole-sextupole magnet of the CC section, the $\beta_{x,y}$, $\alpha_{x,y}$ and $D_{x,px}$ functions are matched with the ones at the entrance of the arc. Therefore, the beta values are reduced by another two orders of magnitude compared to the ones in the CC section.

Arc Section

In the EFF sections, strong dipole components are located in regions with positive dispersion. Thus, the contribution to the momentum compaction factor (α_p) and the phase slip ($\eta_p \sim \alpha_p - 4.5 \times 10^{-10}$) are large. In order to keep the bunches short (small η_p), a negative contribution to α_p is needed and it is developed in the arcs where flexible momentum compaction (FMC) cells [15] are used as building blocks. The optical function and the elements used (same color code as before) for four consecutive FMC cells can be seen in Fig. 3a. Within these FMC cells, the α_p and the 2π closing of the trajectory are independently controlled with two sets of dipoles. Also, in the arcs, the linear tune shift with energy in both transverse planes ($\xi_{x,y}$) is controlled with two sets of combined function dipole-sextupole magnets and the phase advance per FMC cell is $3\pi/2$ (-I transform every second cell). Again, the maximum magnetic field at the magnet aperture is assumed to be 16 T.

Figure 3: Evolution of the optical functions in a) first four FMC cells of the arc and b) the muon collider ring.

Full Ring

Putting all the lattice pieces together, the circumference of the presented ring is 8668.8 m long but without including any straight section for injection/extraction and potential RF cavities that are planned to be placed after the final focusing quadrupoles. If any extra margin up to the planned 10 km circumference remains in future iterations of the ring, it can be used to relax the magnets or performance requirements.

The evolution of the β_x , β_y and D_x in the full ring can be seen in Fig. 3b with red, blue and green curves, respectively.

Particle dynamics studies are also performed and the minimum dynamic aperture (DA_{min}) over 2000 turns without simulating the beam-beam effects for different energy offset values is shown in Table 2. The current version of the collider is approaching the performance requirements shown in Table 1. The most important issues that are not yet addressed is the strong non linear tune shift as well as the tune spread at large p_T s. On the other hand, if the luminosity requirements can be slightly relaxed, for example by doubling β^* , suitable lattice with sufficient acceptances can be extrapolated from the ones presented.

Table 2: Minimum DA for Different p_T Values

p_T [%]	DA_{min} [mm]
0.07	5
0.08	4
0.09	2.5
0.1	<1

CONCLUSION

Muon colliders are proposed as high energy lepton collisions rings without large synchrotron radiation losses. Due to the short muon lifetime, different challenges are addressed with the use of novel design concepts in the presented $\sqrt{s} = 10$ TeV muon collider ring. The present version is not a final one but a work in progress. For any such collider, it is a necessity to keep the circumference small and to cope with the radiation caused by neutrinos. Thus, high magnetic fields and combined function magnets are used extensively. The basic building blocks that are described here are the extended final focusing and arc sections. Given the need for very small β^* s, the compensation of the strong chromatic phenomena is performed right after the final focusing quadrupoles making the design of the extensive final focusing section quite demanding. In the arcs, flexible momentum compaction cells are used as building blocks where the bunch length (through the momentum compaction factor), as well as the linear tune shift with energy are controlled. Particle dynamics studies are also performed and it is shown that the performances of the presented ring are quite close to the luminosity requirements of a $\sqrt{s} = 10$ TeV muon collider, a significant improvement over earlier designs. Future iterations will focus at a refinement of the local CC scheme with further optimized phase of the sextupoles to find a scheme with sufficient acceptances for the 10 TeV muon collider.

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REFERENCES

- [1] I. Zurbano Fernandez *et al.*, “High-luminosity Large Hadron Collider (HL-LHC): Technical design report”, CERN, Geneva, Switzerland, Rep. CERN-2020-01, Dec. 2020.
- [2] D. Schulte, “The international muon collider collaboration”, in *Proc. 12th Int. Particle Accel. Conf. (IPAC’21)*, Campinas, Brazil, May 2021, pp. 3792–3795.
doi:10.18429/JACoW-IPAC2021-THPAB017
- [3] M. Benedikt *et al.*, “Future Circular Collider - European Strategy Update Documents”, CERN, Geneva, Switzerland, Rep. CERN-ACC-2019-0007, Jan. 2019.
- [4] T. K. Charles *et al.*, “The Compact Linear Collider (CLIC) - 2018 Summary Report”, Eds. P. N. Burrows *et al.*, CERN, Geneva, Switzerland, Rep. CERN-2018-005-M, Dec. 2018.
doi:10.23731/CYRM-2018-002.
- [5] F. F. Tikhonin, “On the effects with muon Colliding Beams”, Joint Institute for Nuclear Research, Dubna, Russia, JINR Rep. P2-4120, 1968 (in Russian, translated to English in doi:10.48550/arXiv.0805.3961).
- [6] G. I. Budker, “Accelerators and colliding beams”, in *Proc. 7th Int. Conf. on High-Energy Accelerators (HEACC’69)*, Yerevan, USSR, Aug.-Sep. 1969, published in *Conf. Proc. C*, vol. 690827, pp. 33-39, 1969.
- [7] M. A. Palmer, “The US muon accelerator program”, in *Proc. 15th Int. Particle Accel. Conf. (IPAC’14)*, Dresden, Germany, Jun. 2014, pp. 1367–1369.
doi:10.18429/JACoW-IPAC2014-TUPME012
- [8] MICE collaboration, “Demonstration of cooling by the Muon Ionization Cooling Experiment”, *Nature*, vol. 578, pp. 53–59, 2020. doi:10.1038/s41586-020-1958-9
- [9] D. Alesini *et al.*, “Positron driven muon source for a muon collider”, *arXiv:1905.05747v2*, May 2019.
doi:10.48550/arXiv.1905.05747
- [10] K. Skoufaris *et al.*, “10 TeV center of mass energy muon collider”, in *Proc. 13th Int. Particle Accel. Conf. (IPAC’14)*, pp. 515-518, 2022.
- [11] D. Stratakis *et al.*, “A Muon collider facility for physics discovery”, in *Proc. 2021 US Community Study on the Future of Particle Physics (Snowmass’21)*. doi:10.48550/arXiv.2203.08033.
- [12] N. Bartosik *et al.*, “Simulated detector performance at the muon collider”, in *Proc. 2021 US Community Study on the Future of Particle Physics (Snowmass’21)*. doi:10.48550/arXiv.2203.07964.
- [13] D. Calzolari *et al.*, “Machine-detector interface and background studies for a 10 TeV muon collider”, presented at the IPAC’23, Venice, Italy, May 2023, paper MOPA090, this conference.
- [14] B.W. Montague, “Linear Optics For Improved Chromaticity Correction”, CERN, Geneva, Switzerland, Rep. CERN-LEP-Note-165, Jul. 1979.
- [15] S.Y. Lee, K.Y. Ng, and D. Trbojevic, “Minimizing dispersion in flexible-momentum-compaction lattices”, *Phys. Rev. E*, vol. 48, p. 3040, 1993.
doi:10.1103/PhysRevE.48.3040